

The structure of syntactic stylistic devices in literary texts.

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ABSTRACT:

This article's main goal is to highlight the significance of repetition in textual formulation, which is based on the features of oral form of speech and syntactic stylistic devices that communicate the structural meanings of the latter. In order to properly address this issue, it is crucial to examine how syntactic stylistic devices contribute to the development of functional linguistic styles. This will help to demonstrate the significance of these devices in presenting the major ideas and context of literary texts. . As analyzing any kind of literary text syntactic stylistic devices, that is repetition, chiasmus, stylistic inversion, gradation, ellipsis, antithesis, parallel construction, detached construction and enumeration have the greatest impact. However, according to results of analyzing, repetition is one of the widely used within these syntactic stylistic devices by contrast other models of speech.

KEYWORDS:

Repetition, syntactic, stylistic devices, literary text, scattered, thematic, functional.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to note right away that there is still more work to be done as evidenced by the findings of current fundamental linguistics studies. Numerous studies in the fields of cognitive linguistics, comparative linguistics, and pragmalinguistics have been conducted recently, and some advancement has been made. I. Arnold, I.R. Galperin, as well as researchers from the Uzbek linguists U.D. Ashurova, M.R. Galieva, and J. Jumabaeva, conducted numerous stylistic studies.

The purpose of this work is to shed light on the significance of stylistic devices, particularly repetition in textual formulation that is based on the traits of oral form of speech and stylistic devices which is articulated the structural meanings of the syntactic stylistic devices. The term "syntactic stylistic devices" (abbreviated as "SDs") is used in the following sections of the article. It is made clear during the theoretical analysis of the work that it is crucial to examine the function of syntactic SDs in the development of functional

linguistic styles in order to support the significance of these SDs in presenting the major logic and contextual meanings in literary writings. . One of the main object of studying the role syntactic SDs in the interrelation of the text and different structural meaning and the full disclosure of the meaning of literary texts and contextual meaning. We know, analyzing the syntactic stylistic means is a significant in establishing close interrelationship in stylistics. Interrelation of the text and various content meanings and the role of syntactic SDs in the full disclosure of literary text and contextual meanings to simplify concepts in the study of theory.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Stylistic devices are intentional combinations of expressive and figurative language elements at many levels (phonetic, graphic, grammatical, lexical, and textual) with dynamically changing functions, such as amplification, displacement, or generalization. [1, p.10]. Expressive means are set of morphological, syntactical, world-building of forms language, which may be used for emotive enhancement of speech and logical accentuating. Expressive means are part of speech.

English's syntactic SDs can be split into three categories:

1. Syntactic SDs rely on the purposeful deletion of some sentence components to reduce the sentence model. Aposiopesis, asyndeton, and ellipsis are all members of this category.
2. Syntactic SDs, which extend the sentence model by include new features or by purposeful repetition. Repetition, enumeration, chiasmus, and polysyndeton all belong to this group.
3. Syntactic SDs rely on purposeful sentence fragmentation or a disruption in the grammatical phrase's set word order. This category includes rhetorical devices such as inversion, detachment, parallel construction, and rhetorical query [2, pp. 139–158].

employing aesthetic techniques and expressive methods frequently seen as a type of linguistic deviation. Joseph, a French linguist, claims The artistic approach of Vandries is always a response. It is an argot and goes against common language. It takes many shapes. [3, p.251]. SDs of expressive means are those that are syntactic. That together make a full syntactic framework, which is regarded as their most typical characteristic. One of the Syntactic SDs is the techniques for generating using syntactic-intonation expressiveness in literature and the arts fulfill a particular methodological task. Specific syntactic turnovers are known as syntactic SDs. that aid in enhancing the emotional impact of speech, This involves repetition, parallelism, and its kinds, ellipses, antithesis, stylistic inversion, and gradation.

Repetition is one of the most widely utilized syntactic SDs in literary language. A SD called repetition is most frequently employed to convey extiment. Speech that is emotionally charged tends to be brief, logical, and repetitive of the same ideas. With the goal of

discovering the solution, numerous conversations about repetition are conducted. The New Fowler's Modern English Usage argues that repeats in typical grammatical constructions might sometimes be unintentional in the beginning. If the same words are repeated too close together, repetition might be unwanted. One issue that is regularly brought up is incorrect usage. For instance, Preminger and Brogan assert that its excessive use by poets is the root of its incorrect use [6, p. 1035]. According to McArthur, repetition is typically avoided in formal writing "for the purpose of economy and in favor of a tradition of exquisite variation." [7, p.862]. We can observe the repetition of certain words and in some cases word combinations in the spoken language. E.g. "She shrieked loudly: "where is my baby? But where is my baby? I want to know where is my baby?" (A. Bennet.). In this sentence we can see that the phrase "where is my baby?" is repetition, however according to some opinions, it doesn't fulfilled a SD here. It simply expresses a certain excited state of the speaker. Since an ecstatic person's speech is constantly fragmented and irrational, it is normal to utilize repeated words, phrases, word groups, and sentences. The majority of linguists believe that repetition is not a standard deviation (SD) if it reveals the speaker's ecstatic emotions, as seen in the prior case. . The scientific observers which follows to this idea, consider that repetition doesn't show emotional state but just concentrate on logical emphasis of the utterance. On the contrary, we are against this idea as we consider that repetition is one of the syntactic SD and have its origin in the emotive language. Describing logical emphasis in the sentences are really very crucial in case of repetition. By repeating certain words, word combinations, phrases or clauses, readers are reminded of their importance and is used them as key words, phrases, clauses or sentences of the text by writers. As it has been contradicted above, repetitio ought to be considered as a SD when it is not only repeated for logical emphasis but also to indicate a speaker's emotional state.

Repetition is classified according to its structure and compositional design.

1. If the repeated words, word combinations or phrases come at the beginning of the sentences or clauses, it is called anaphora. E.g. "Ignorant of how soarnes had watched her, ignorant of Fleur's reckless desperation...- ignorant of all this everybody felt aggrieved ". (Galsworthy).
Preminger and Brogan comment that anaphora is favored because its structure reinforces the meaning of words.
2. The opposite to anaphora is epiphora (or epistrophe) which "repeats words at the ends of clauses, lines or stanzas" [6, p. 73]. If the repeated unit is placed in the final of the phrases, sentences or clauses this type of words or word combinations is called epiphora. E.g. " The clerks rattle me. The wickets rattle me, the sights of money rattle me, everything rattles me".
3. In some cases, a syntactical unit which is placed at the beginning, is repeated at the end and it is called frame repetition. This structural type of repetition mostly used in poetry and it is most effective in singling out paragraphs. Our hands have met , but not our hearts; Our hands will never meet again. Friends, if we have ever been Friends, we can't

now remain: I only know I loved you once, I only know I loved in vain. Our hands have met, but not our hearts. Our hands will never meet again. (Thomas Hood).

4. The fourth model of repetition is anadiplosis. In this type of repetition an utterance words or phrases are repeated in the last also at the beginning of the next sentences or clauses. E.g. "All service ranks the same with God, With God whose puppets, best and worst, are we". (Robert Browning). Anadiplosis serves to emphasis the most important parts of the sentences.

A word, a phrase, a clause, or a sentence appears multiple times across the entire text in accordance with classification. Although the scattered repetition model's goal is the same as that of all other models of repetition, it differs structurally from every other kind of repetition that now exists. Because dispersed repetition is evident throughout the text without any discernible pattern, we came to the conclusion that it is scattered repetition.

E.g. His mouth had been open for some time, but he extended it wider. It was dry and cracked. He made a feeble attempt to utter "Posse." ("The final Bullet," M. Kantor).

Another result of investigation is called thematic repetition. In this type of repetition, without any certain types of repetition, the theme of the text is repeated. Modern researchers indicate A. Coppard's short story "Tribute" as a good example of thematic repetition. E.g. The country paid them tribute, and therefore, as the Regents' wealth continued to flow in, they helped their country more and more; they even lent the tribute back to the country and received yet more tribute for that

Conclusion

In conclusion, repetition is frequently viewed as unwanted and careless. It is debatable if repetition is helpful or not as a result. It is generally accepted that repetition can be harmful, but only if it is done carelessly or insufficiently. "Linguists are therefore faced with the paradox that repetition is widely utilized, yet frequently avoided," writes Aitcheson in this regard.

[8, p.18]. In contrast, Quirk claims that lexical repetition is typically avoided because it can come off as intrusive. Additionally, he emphasizes that repetition is acceptable in legal terminology to avoid misunderstanding. However, repetition is frequently utilized to create emphasis in non-specialized writings [9, p.144].

There is no simple way to respond to the topic of whether repetition is good or bad. In their book "The King's English," H.W. Fowler and F.G. Fowler state that "we have repeat instances that are good in themselves; we have repetition examples that are neither very good nor particularly evil in them, but that offend simply by recurrence." [10, p.211]. Repetition might be seen as helpful or worthless depending on how well the speaker uses it, to sum up these topics. By examining the sources, it can be said that two new types of repetition, scattered and thematic repetition, have been identified in modern English in addition to the old model of repetition. The emotional intensity of both fresh forms of

repetitions is comparable to others although both of them are less mentioned in the research works.

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